

the unsprayed control plot as well as the surrounding plots, it produced no damage in any of the Phosvel-treated plots. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in chemicals on the control of root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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Seeds of IR8 were soaked in a 4-ml test solution of each of 32 chemicals at doses of 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm for 12 and 24 h, or equivalent to doses of 0.2, 0.4, and 0.8 g/100 g seed with water control. Treated seeds were sown in soil inoculated with infective larvae of

M. graminicola. Nematicides and insecticides were effective to varying degrees in reducing the endoparasites and egg mass production. Among fungicides, only thiobendazole was effective (see table). Herbicides were phytotoxic; growth regulators and hormones were less effective; amino acids were ineffective. Oxamyl, fensulfothion, and phorate reduced endoparasites by more than 60% and egg masses by 80%. Carbofuran inhibited endoparasites, but was less effective in reducing egg mass production. Oxamyl at 500 and 1,000 ppm was as effective as other chemicals at higher doses either as 12- or 24-h seed-soak treatment. All herbicides affected seed viability and hormones, and growth regulators affected growth. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in pesticides on invasion and development of *Meloidogyne graminicola*. Minimum nematode incidence at 2,000 ppm.

Treatment	Endoparasites (no.)	Egg masses (no.)	Germination (%)
<i>Nematicides and insecticides</i>			
Oxamyl	15.0	2.2	100
DBCP	23.1	5.5	100
Chlorpyrifos	18.0	6.1	100
Phorate	18.5	3.2	100
Carbofuran	30.2	3.2	100
Mephospholan	31.2	9.2	100
Fensulfothion	18.0	3.5	100
Quinalphos	25.1	7.1	95
<i>Fungicides</i>			
Mebenil	52.5	15.0	100
Bavistin	54.0	16.2	100
Thiabendazole	39.5	14.1	85
Cela - 50	50.0	16.5	92
Control	51.2	17.7	100

Whitebacked planthopper outbreak in Bangladesh

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The whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* is a minor rice pest in Bangladesh. Two outbreaks of the pest were recorded in deep-water rice in 1963 (March–December and May–June). In 1967, the pest occurred in aus rice (March–August) and in deep-water rice during July in Comilla district. During the early 1970's, the pest was the

dominant hopper in the aus season in Mymensingh area, making up 61% of the total hopper population. But during the transplanted aman season (July–December), it ranked fourth and made up about 10% of the population.

In mid-April 1977, hopperbum due to *S. furcifera* was observed on the boro season crop (November–May) of IR8 in a patch of 55.74 sq m in the Mohammadpur area of Dacca. The crop was in the milky to dough stage; the plot was irrigated by sewage water. The population on 18 April was more than 1,000 adults and nymphs/hill. Loss was estimated at about 80% of the expected yield. ❧

Parasites of grasshopper eggs associated with paddy in Pakistan

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Scelio spp. are important parasites of grasshopper eggs. Six species parasitize grasshoppers that attack paddy in Pakistan. The widely distributed and adaptable parasites can withstand severely cold winters by hibernating as first-instar larvae in the host eggs. In summer the parasite adults are found mostly in shady places where they are protected from excessive heat; when dense vegetation is lacking, they creep into crevices.

Scelio do not parasitize all eggs in large egg pods, but egg pods with no more than 25 eggs are completely parasitized. Freshly laid host eggs are preferred to old ones.

The patchy distribution of host eggs may not allow enough of the parasites to develop to provide a high level of grasshopper control. Although *Scelio* do not seem to play a dominant role, they are in position to eliminate many eggs in the late fall. That could reduce the nymphal population in the spring and result in fewer adults in the summer. ❧

Subsequent infectivity of treated *Meloidogyne* larvae in chemicals

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Larvae of *Meloidogyne graminicola* were held in aerated distilled water for 24 h after direct contact for 48 h with nematicides, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, amino acids, growth regulators, and hormones at different levels. The contact toxicity tests showed that the following chemicals resulted in more than 90% mortality: oxamyl (nematicide) and propanil (herbicide) at 50 ppm and above; fensulfothion (insecticide) at 100 ppm; quinalphos (insecticide) and DBCP (nematicide) at 200 ppm; ZR-777 (hormone) at 500 ppm; and cycocel (growth regulator) at 1,000 ppm. DL forms of amino acids, fungicides, and other growth regulators were

ineffective. Carbofuran among insecticides and DBCP among nematicides were less effective than oxamyl or fensulfothion.

Inoculation of these larvae to roots of IR8 showed that root invasion was impaired by treatments at sublethal concentrations of propanil, fensulfothion, and oxamyl at 25 ppm; and of DBCP, phorate, and chlorpyrifos (insecticides) at 100 ppm. Carbofuran at 200 ppm adversely affected the larval penetration although it gave less direct contact mortality. ZR-777 and Diethyl sulfate (hormones) were effective at 250 to 500 ppm and above, while quinalphos, mephospholan (insecticides), 2,4-D, butachlor, MCPA (herbicides), IAA, IBA, NAA, maleic hydrazide, and gibberellic acid (growth regulators) had no persistent or inhibitory toxicity.

Soildrench pesticide treatment to control the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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Twelve pesticides were tested as postinoculation soil-drench treatments for effectiveness in control of the root-knot nematode *M. graminicola*. The doses 25, 50, 100, and 200 ppm were adjusted to 3.75 to 30 kg/ha. Phorate, oxamyl, fensulfothion, and carbofuran were significantly superior to DBCP, chlorpyrifos, quinalphos, and emphospholan. The fungicides mebenil, bavistin, thiabendazole, and cela-50 were less effective. Oxamyl and fensulfothion at 50 ppm and above, and DBCP and phorate at 100 ppm, were equally effective in reducing egg masses and endoparasites. Carbofuran significantly controlled egg mass production.

Preplanting and postplanting soil-drench treatments in the fields showed that oxamyl, phorate, carbofuran, and fensulfothion at 15 kg/ha were equally effective in reducing the development of the nematodes and the production of egg masses in roots. These treatments markedly reduced the larval population in the soils regardless of time of application. Oxamyl and fensulfothion

inhibited giant cell development at sites of nematode establishment. The dimensions of the giant cells and

developing nematodes were reduced in the postplanting soil application of these systemic pesticides.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Sensitivity of rice field alga *Chara* sp. to different chemicals

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Green algae of different morphology and growth habit and belonging to different genera grow extensively in transplanted paddy fields in India; the most common is *Chara* sp. These organisms not only compete with rice plants for space and nutrients but appear to hinder tillering. Use of copper sulfate and other chemicals for their control has not been successful.

Some fungicides, insecticides, and synthetic detergents were screened for

algicidal activity against *Chara* grown in waterlogged soil in pots. The water was replaced with chemical treatments of desired concentration and the time required for complete alga death was recorded. Nine of 16 fungicides were good inhibitors at low concentration. They include the organic tin compounds Brestan 60 and Brestanol (see table). The carbamates Dithane M-45 and TMTD were found to be inhibitory even at 0.007% concentration. Among the insecticides and detergents, thiodan and the two detergents are equally inhibitory. The algicidal properties of these chemicals at such low concentrations are encouraging.

Algicidal activity of some fungicides, insecticides, and other chemicals against *Chara* sp. (av. of four replications). West Bengal, India.

Chemical	Days after treatment until death at percent concentration of whole formulation							
	1	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.06	0.03	0.015	0.007
<i>Fungicides</i>								
Blotox-50	2	2	3	3	4	4	4	ND ^a
Dithane 2-78	1	1	2	4	5	6	ND	
Dithane M-45	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	4
TMTD 75WPP	1	1	1	2	2	2	4	4
Starcraft 83WP	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	ND
Difolatan 80WP	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
Brestanol45	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	3
Brestan 60	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	3
Brassicol 75WP	2	2	2	3	3	4	5	ND
Hinosan 50EC	ND							
Bavistin	ND							
Topsin M	ND							
Allisan	ND							
Benodanil	ND							
Kasumin	ND							
<i>Insecticides and other chemicals</i>								
Thiodan 35EC	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
Accothon 1000	1	1	2	2	3	4	ND	
Diazinon G.	2	3	ND					
Disyston G.	ND							
Sultaf. 80WP	ND							
Idet-20	0.5	0.5	1	1	2	2	3	3
Swascifix 45	0.5	0.5	1	1	2	2	3	3
Det. (Washing)	1	1	1	1	2	2	4	ND
Copper sulfate	1	2	2	3	3	3	4	4

^aND = no death.